

NOTES

The present investigation shows that the amine-exchange reaction can occur with good yield when the reacting amine is more basic than the liberated amine^{4,6}. Alkylamines being more basic than ammonia can replace it easily. The rate of amine exchange reaction is dependent on the relative bulk of the incoming and outgoing amines. Rate of reaction is slow in case of propyl and *iso*-propyl amines.

The IR spectra of mixed-imine Schiff base complexes of nickel show a -N-H stretching frequency at 3300 cm⁻¹. The disappearance of the 3300 cm⁻¹ band after amine exchange reaction can be attributed to the replacement of the N-H hydrogen in nickel mixed imine Schiff base complexes by an alkyl group.

Ni(II) square planar complexes are expected to be diamagnetic. The Ni(II) complexes, however, exhibit paramagnetism ($\mu = 2.8$ to 3.4 B.M.). This can be attributed to polymerization leading to distorted octahedral structure¹¹⁻¹⁴.

The visible spectra of Ni(II) paramagnetic complexes show a shoulder at 610 to 630 nm ($\epsilon = 50$ to 80). There are no bands at higher wavelength region showing square planar structure. The reflectance spectra of the complexes have also been obtained. They exhibit rise in optical density beyond 900 nm indicating distorted octahedral structure. This supports polymerization in the solid state. In solution the polymerization breaks, resulting in the square planar structure.

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Mechanism of Electroreduction of Nickel(II) Complexes

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In the *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 1976 ; 14A, 410, H. S. Sharma and H. L. Nigam have published a paper entitled "Correlation of spectral and redox properties of some nickel(II) complexes of thiomalic acid and thiovanol" in which the authors have proposed a mechanism of electron transfer for the electro-reduction of the nickel(II) complexes which is identical to what had been proposed earlier¹ based on studies on some nickel(II) complexes, which was in fact an extension of the ideas based on earlier studies on some copper(II) complexes². Subsequently on the basis of studies on several nickel(II) complexes of different charge type (cationic, non-ionic and anionic) a more refined mechanism has been suggested³. This correlates well the ease of electron transfer with the ligand field splitting parameter for a series of nickel(II) complexes of a particular charge type, i.e. enables a general correlation of the spectral and redox properties of these complexes.

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